

IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR MANAGING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF REGIONAL UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation: In the article main factors of developing mechanisms for managing the competitiveness of regional universities are highlighted. In addition to this classification of competitiveness and its level are noted.

Key words: *global competition, conscious fostering, productivity, long-term output, human capital, income, infrastructure.*

Nowadays, globalization and other factors are changing and influencing the competitiveness of different areas. These processes are like organizers of the regional setup and therefore need to be considered. In the world competition, things like knowledge or social connections become very important and help the economy grow. In the study of regions, having knowledge is seen as an important part of how regions grow and improve. Knowledge has become the most important thing for making things, and it is seen as a new way to help the economy. This means that we need to think again about how important knowledge, new ideas, technology, and learning are. To put it simply, developed countries have an advantage because they are good at creating and using knowledge. Universities have also a significant role in the shaping of these processes, as their educational and research priorities are widened by the conscious fostering of social and economic development. Nowadays it is more

and more accepted that not only enterprises but different regions also compete with each other.

Competitiveness means how well a person or business can compete in a global market. This is very important in today's world because of how connected and competitive the global economy is. In this study, we will use a common definition of competitiveness: to be able to make a lot of money and create jobs while facing competition from other countries and areas. We can see that competitiveness includes the impact of innovation and research and development (which mostly come from universities) on having an advantage in the competition. According to Lengyel (2003), if the wages do not decrease in an economy and they are not low and the products can be considered competitive, meaning that they are not more expensive and are also marketable, then this can be only achievable due to continuous innovation and technological change. By innovation, productivity is enhanced. The essential requirements of this are research and development activities and the transfer of knowledge.

The pyramid model of competitiveness is based on a clear definition of competitiveness that is easy to understand. It focuses on two important aspects: how much money people make and how many jobs are available. This definition is complicated because it applies to both different types of businesses and different areas. At the top of the model, we can find the main objective, which is to improve people's living conditions and overall happiness. There are two groups of factors that affect competitiveness based on how they relate to economic development. Some factors that affect how an area grows economically are called development factors. These factors can improve how well businesses in the area can compete with each other. The other group consists of factors that are mainly beyond the economy, they explain the region's competitiveness in the long-term but economic development programs can barely affect them (Lengyel 2003). Among the basic categories and development factors the model represents the

influential factors that can be connected to innovation The effects of universities on economy can be categorized in two groups (Lengyel 2008): Short-term input effects and long-term output effects. Universities spend a significant amount of money to maintain and operate its own buildings. These services are ordered from local enterprises. The students, professors and research associates also spend some part of their earnings locally.

Having a university nearby helps the local community in many ways. It brings in more money for the government and creates a need for more public services. The immediate impacts of the university on the community include changes in the amount of people wanting to use local businesses, the money coming in and going out of local homes, and the money and services provided by the local government. Because of universities, many young and well-educated individuals enter the job market. Local people who have learned new skills and abilities are able to easily begin their own businesses. Because of this, educational institutions are becoming more attractive options for people who want to become entrepreneurs. Young people who have just finished their studies can get jobs that companies from other areas are interested in. This can help create new job opportunities. The professors and researches of the university practice significant R&D activities (Lengyel 2008). The long-term effects of universities (output side) can affect the qualification of human capital, the attraction of foreign capital and workforce into the proximity of the university and the number of enterprises based on university research. The input factors can be considered as triggers of secondary regional multiplier effects of the economic base model, as they vivify demand regarding local services. However this demand does not generate substantive economic growth and barely creates new workplaces. The output factors trigger primary multiplier effects. New companies could come into existence that can create new workplaces in the region and are able to acquire income from outside the region.

Summing up all given information above, it should be noted that in connection with factor conditions the human resources and infrastructure have the greatest significance, so here we can highlight the importance of both hard and soft elements. Here those factors are located that serve as a foundation of the competitiveness of universities. If professors are more qualified and if the infrastructure is more modern, the universities can accomplish a better position on the virtual global rankings of universities. Demand conditions mean demand for all factors that serve as an output of the university. The sophisticated local demand motivates the universities from aspects of education, research and third mission. These are necessary but not sufficient requirements of internationally recognized competitiveness. In accordance with the input side it is important that highly qualified graduates with sophisticated knowledge should appear on the labor market on the output side.

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